

HOLISTIC AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF STHOULYA: AN INTEGRATIVE CASE STUDY

Parikshitha K.R.*¹, Dr Supreeth M.J.²

¹3rd Year Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Sri kalabyraveshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Panchakarma, Sri Kalabyraveshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

*Corresponding Author: Parikshitha K.R.

3rd year Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Sri kalabyraveshwara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152239>

How to cite this Article: Parikshitha K.R.*¹, Dr Supreeth M.J.². (2026). HOLISTIC AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF STHOULYA: AN INTEGRATIVE CASE STUDY. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 178–182. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/12/2025

Article Revised on 25/12/2025

Article Published on 05/01/2026

ABSTRACT

This study explores the effectiveness of an integrative medical approach incorporating ayurveda, pathya and yoga in the holistic management of sthaulya (obesity). The work is based on a conceptual and literature-based analysis of classical texts, supplemented by relevant contemporary clinical research. Emphasis is placed on ahara, vihara, and yogic practices aimed at restoring metabolic balance. Selected traditional herbal preparations were reviewed for their roles in fat metabolism and detoxification. Ayurveda explain obesity as a consequence of kapha–meda dhatu vitiation, leading to impaired digestion and ama formation. Integrative regimens that combine Laghu, non-unctuous, and metabolism-stimulating diets with yoga practices such as Surya namaskar, Kapala Bhati, and mindfulness meditation were found to support lipid metabolism, reduce psychological stress, and enhance overall vitality. Overall, the integrative use of ayurveda, dietary discipline, and yoga offers a multidimensional strategy for obesity management by addressing physical, metabolic, and psychological dimensions. This synergistic approach supports sustainable weight management and contributes to the prevention of modern lifestyle disorders.

KEYWORDS: Integrative, obesity management, ayurveda, yoga therapy, pathya.

INTRODUCTION

Obesity has become a major global health challenge, driven by sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy dietary patterns, and psychological stress. According to the world health organization (WHO) nearly 1 in 6 adults worldwide is affected by obesity.^[1,2], highlighting its growing public health burden. Obesity is a complex metabolic disorder associated with diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and reduced quality of life.

Ayurveda conceptualizes obesity (sthaulya) as a disorder of kapha–meda dhatu^[3], impaired agni^[4], and accumulation of ama, resulting from faulty ahara and vihara. Ayurveda emphasizes ahara and vihara as key factors in prevention and management through a balanced diet, physical activity, and disciplined living. In recent years, integrative approaches combining ayurvedic

principles, dietary regulation (pathya), and yoga have gained attention for their holistic^[5] and sustainable role in obesity management.

CASE

□ A 32-year-old male patient presents with progressive weight gain over the past five years, accompanied by dyslipidemia and prediabetic status. He also reports a tendency toward emotional eating.

CHIEF COMPLAINTS

□ Increased weight in the last 5 years

ASSOCIATED COMPLAINTS

□ Complains of persistent lethargy, fatigue, and loss of interest in routine activities.

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

- A 32-year-old male software engineer from Delhi complains of weight gain, lethargy, loss of interest, and emotional eating for 5 years. He was diagnosed with prediabetes and dyslipidemia at a nearby clinic 2 months back. Due to stress and reduced work performance, he has come for integrated treatment to improve his health.

PAST HISTORY

- Prediabetic since 2 months
- Dyslipidemia in the last 2 months – FBS- 106

FAMILY HISTORY

- No one in family is obese

PERSONAL HISTORY AND ANTHROPOMETRIC

Aahara	Mixed diet/non vegetarian twice in a week. Late night eating - junk
Vihara	Sedentary life style (day sleep, rathri jagara due to work)
Appetite	Good
Bowels	Regular, 1/day
Micturition	Regular, 1 at night
Sleep	Sound (sometimes disturbed due to urge to pass urine at night)

Blood Pressure	120/80 mm/Hg
Pulse Rate	76 bpm
Height	175 cms
Weight	111kg
Body mass Index(BMI)	36.2 kg/m ²
Chest Circumference	109cms
Abdomen Circumference	120 cms
Mid Arm Circumference (Right and left)	40cms 41cms
Mid Thigh Circumference (Right, Left)	62cms 60cms
Waist Circumference	120cms
Hip Circumference	120cms

DASHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

- Prakriti: Kaphapitta
- Vikriti: Kapha, Meda
- Sara: Madhyama
- Samhanana: Pravara
- Satva: Madhyama
- Satmya: Pravara
- Aharashakti: Pravara
- Vyayamashakti: Avara
- Pramana: Adhika
- Vaya: Madyama

ASTASTHANAPAREEKSHA

- Nadi: Prakruta
- Mala: Prakruta
- Mootra: Prakruta
- Jihva: Aliptata
- Shabda: Prakruta
- Sparsha: Prakruta
- Drik: Prakruta
- Aakruti: Sthoola

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

- ✓ CVS: S1, S2 heard
- ✓ RS: NVBS heard
- ✓ CNS: Well oriented
- ✓ P/A: Soft, No Organomegally

MEASUREMENTS**WHO CLASSIFICATION OF WEIGHT STATUS^[6]**

Classification	BMI (kg/m ²)
Underweight	<18.50
Normal range	18.50 – 24.99
Overweight	≥25.00
Pre-obesity	25.00 – 29.99
Obesity	≥30.00
Obesity class 1	30.00 – 34.99
Obesity class 2	35.00 -39.99
Obesity class 3	≥40.00

SAMPRAPTI OF STHOULYA^[7]

SAMPRAPTI GHATAKAS

Udbhava Sthana: Amashaya;
 Vyaktasthana: Sarva Shareera;
 Adhistana: Medo dhatu;
 Roga marga: Bahya;
 Agni: Teekshnagni;

Dosha: Kapha and Vata;
 Dushya: Rasa, Mamsa and Medo dhatu;
 Srotas: Rasavaha, Medovaha ;
 Sroto dusti: Sanga;
 Sadhya Asadhyata: Krichra Sadhya

TREATMENT PLAN

Days	Treatment	Medicines Used	Observations
Day 1-3	Deepana- Pachana	1. Dashamoola Haritaki (1tsp With Warm Water Before Sleep) 2. Vaisvanara Choorna (1tsp-0-1tsp With Warm Water Before Food) 3. Gandarvastadhi Kshaya (15ml-0-15ml With 30ml Warm Water After Food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Appetite Increased ▪ Bowel Regular And Clear ▪ Feels Light After Evacuation
Day 4	Sadyo Virechana ^[8] (Priorly Sarvanga Abhyanga Followed By Baspa Sweda)	1. SA- Dhanwantram Thaila 2. Trivruit Lehya (AVP) – 30 Grams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ VEGAS- 8 Vegas ▪ Tiredness During Vegas ▪ Lightness At End Of The Day
Day 5-21	Udvardana Followed By Baspa Sweda	1. Triphala Choorna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Noticed Inch Reduction Around The Abdomen ▪ Feels Light And Fresh ▪ Lethargy Reduced ▪ Feels More Energetic

YOGAAND PRANAYAMA

Yoga (HATAYOGA)	Timings	Observation
Suryakriya	4am- 4:30am	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased Mobility ▪ Able To Sit In Ardha Siddhasana For A Longer Duration ▪ Can Walk More Than 10,000 Steps ▪ Improved Concentration And Clarity Of Thought ▪ Feels Lightness In The Body And Calmness Of Mind
Suryashakthi	4:30am-5:30am	
Yogaasanas	5:45am-7am	
Angamardhana	5:30pm-6:30pm	
Sukha Kriya (Breath Watching)	3-4 Times In A Day For 20mins 1 Sitting	
Listening To Consecrated Chants	Throughout The Day	

PATHYA

Day	Diet Given	Observation
Day 5-11	Ash gourd juice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helps in detoxification and cooling the body Provides essential fiber and micronutrients Easy to digest and nourishing Aids in weight control and gut health
Day 12-14	Millet kanji with veggies	
Day 15- 17	Raw and boiled veg salad	
Day 18-21	50% raw and 50% cooked food	

SHAMANA OUSHADHI

Days	Medicines
From Day 9-14	Gayatriadi Kashaya (15ml-0-15ml With 30ml Warm Water) Dhanwantarm Gulika (1-0-1) Hepacure Syrup (15ml-0-15ml) Yogaraja Guguulu (1-0-1) Madhuram Capsules (2-0-2) Triphala Churna (0-0-1tsp)
From Day 15-21	Guggulu Tiktaka Kashaya (15ml-0-15ml With 30ml Warm Water) Ayaskriti (10ml-0-10ml) Hepacure Syrup (10ml-0-10ml) Navaka Guggulu (2-0-2) Madhuram Capsules (2-0-2)

ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS RESULTS

	Before	After
Weight	111kg	99kg
BMI	36.2 kg/m ²	32.33 kg/m ²
Chest Circumference	109cms	99cms
Abdomen Circumference	120 cms	97cms
Mid Arm Circumference (Right and left)	40cms 41cms	32cms 30cms
Mid Thigh Circumference (Right and left)	62cms 60cms	53cms 51cms
Waist Circumference	120cms	110cms
Hip Circumference	120cms	100cms

SYMPTOMS WISE CHANGES (score out of 10)

	Before	After
Lethargy	10	4
Fatigue	8	3
Loss Of Interest In Routine Activities.	9	5

❖ FBS- Value Reduced From 106 To 98

DISCUSSION

- ❖ Action of udwarthana and bhashpa sweda: their *ruksha guna* helps remove *srotorodha*, liquefies and mobilizes excess *meda dhatu*.^[9]
- ❖ *Virechana* with *trivrit lehyam*^[10] promotes *medoharana*.
- ❖ *Vyayama*^[11]: improve fat metabolism, enhance *dhatu agni*, provide shape and firmness to the body.
- ❖ *Pathya* : a low-calorie, high-fiber diet follows the principle of “*guru cha atarpanam*”^[12] — heavy yet non-nourishing food that pacifies *vata* and *agni* while reducing *meda* and *kapha*.
- ❖ Diagnosis & cause: *sthoulya*, one of the metabolic disorders, results from excessive fat accumulation causing *meda* and *mamsa dhatu* excess.^[13]
- ❖ Treatment & response: the patient underwent *udwarthana*, *sadhyovirechana* followed *pathya*, *vyayama*, meditation experiencing lightness in the body, mind and proper *samyaka lakshanas* post-procedure.
- ❖ Outcome: significant improvement was noted in symptoms, weight, bmi, anthropometric value.^[14]

CONCLUSION

- ❖ *Sthoulya* can be effectively managed through *Apatharpana Chikitsa*^[15,16] with *Nidana Parivarjana*, *Shamana*, *Shodhana*, diet, *vyayama* and behavioral modifications.
- ❖ Significant improvement observed in symptoms, weight, BMI, anthropometric Measures.^[17]
- ❖ Long-term success requires continuous motivation and adoption of healthy *Ahara*, *Vihara*,

Dinacharya^[18,19] and *Ritucharya*.

- ❖ For successful weight loss to become permanent, an individual has to adopt new behaviors to maintain weight loss^[20]

REFERENCE

1. World health organization. Obesity and overweight. Geneva: world health organization, 2023.
2. World health organization. Global health estimates: overweight and obesity. Geneva: WHO., 2022.
3. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, revised by charaka and dridhabala, with *ayurveda dipika* commentary of chakrapani datta. Sutra sthana, ashtau ninditiya adhyaya (21). Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan; reprint ed.
4. Sharma R, dash B. *Charaka samhita: text with english translation and critical exposition*. Vol 1. Varanasi: chowkhamba sanskrit series office, 2014.
5. Telles S, sharma SK, yadav A, singh N. Yoga as a therapeutic intervention in the management of obesity. *J. altern complement med.*, 2010; 16(6): 669-674.
6. BMI chart for obesity [internet]. Who. 2017 [cited 25 mach 2017]. Available from: <https://www.Euro.Who.Int/en/health-topics/disease-prevention/nutrition/a-healthy-lifestyle/body-mass-index-bmi>.
7. Nadkarni shailesh. *Arogya mandir medhorog visheshank* published by shree dhootapapeshwar ltd, March 2008; 1-8.
8. Rasendra saṅgraha. *Rasāyana prakaraṇa*. In: tripathi I, editor. *Rasendra saṅgraha with rasavidyotini hindi commentary*. Varanasi: chaukhambha sanskrit bhawan; reprint ed., 52-53.
9. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana, 22/11–12 (*langhana-brimhaniya adhyaya*). In: sharma RK, dash B, editors. Varanasi: chaukhambha sanskrit series office; reprint ed.
10. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, kalpasthana, 7/28–30 (*virechana kalpa*). In: tripathi BN, editor. Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan.
11. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana, 7/31–33 (*vyayama vidhana*). In: sharma RK, dash B, editors. Varanasi: chaukhambha sanskrit series office.
12. Susruta. *Susruta samhita*, sutrasthana, 15/37–38 (*anna-pana vidhi*). In: srikantha murthy KR, editor. Varanasi: chaukhambha orientalia.
13. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana, 21/3–4

- (aṣṭau-ninditīya adhyāya). In: sharma RK, dash B. Varanasi: chaukhambha sanskrit series office.
14. World health organization. *Obesity and overweight*. WHO fact sheet, 2023.
 15. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana; ashtauninditiya adhyaya (ch. Su. 21/3–4). Commentary by chakrapani datta. Reprint ed. Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan, 2018; 117–118.
 16. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana; santarpaniya adhyaya (ch. Su. 23/3–5). Chakrapani commentary. Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan, 2018; 122–124.
 17. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana; langhanabrimhaniya adhyaya (ch. Su. 22/9–11). Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan, 2018; 119–120.
 18. Sushruta. *Sushruta samhita*, chikitsasthana; sthauilya chikitsa adhyaya (su. Chi. 15/37–40). Dalhana commentary. Varanasi: chaukhambha orientalia; 2019. P. 276–278. Vagbhata. *Ashtanga hridaya*, sutrasthana; dinacharya adhyaya (A.H. Su. 2/10–12). Arundatta commentary. Varanasi: chaukhambha orientalia, 2018; 24–25.
 19. Agnivesha. *Charaka samhita*, sutrasthana; matrashitiya adhyaya (ch. Su. 5/12–13). Varanasi: chaukhambha surbharati prakashan, 2018; 71–72.
 20. Deshpande H, saraganacharya SV. Ayurvedic approach in the management of sthoulya – A case study. (International journal of ayurvedic medicine, 13(1): 106-110.